

Cashless NFC-based Payment in Festivals: LINDDUN Privacy Threat Model

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Cashless payment is becoming increasingly ubiquitous and with this overall trend, also the adoption of non-bank-led payment solutions keeps increasing. In this document, we provide the standalone application description of an abstracted payment system used in the context of mass events such as festivals. These payment systems commonly use of parallel festival-specific currency (voucher or token-based) and use contactless communication technology such as NFC for payment convenience. The abstracted payment system described in this document is based on a survey of technologies adopted in diverse festivals and the technical information system architecture in support of such payment operations. We first present the overall case description, consisting of two distinct Data Flow Diagrams (DFDs) and a step-by-step explanation of the main functioning of this system. Then, we present the LINDDUN privacy threat model for this case, which lists and describes the most prevalent privacy threats.

1 Introduction

This report presents a case study application of the LINDDUN privacy threat modeling framework. It is comprised of two parts: (i) an in-depth case description, and (ii) detailed threat descriptions.

Part I of this report is based on the work conducted within the context and scope of the master's thesis entitled '*Cashless Payment at Festivals: A Security and Privacy Threat Modeling Analysis*' by Mustafa Kurtoglu, Michaël Teugels and Joachim Wyckmans^{1,2}, supervised by Dimitri Van Landuyt and Jakob De Moor. This work was awarded a master's thesis prize by the Faculty of Economics and Business of KU Leuven in 2025. This part of the report is structured as follows: First, a number of scoping decisions are explained and motivated, based on the availability of technical information, popularity, etc. More concretely, a representative festival payment system is chosen in Section 2. Then, Section 3 introduces the main DFD models of the application, and discusses their elements and main flows. Section 3 shows the DFDs of the system, explains these in additional detail, and presents a DFD glossary.

Part II is based on the combined threat model outputs of four distinct threat modelers: Dimitri Van Landuyt, Laurens Sion, Felix Schwickerath, and Tom Hüller. It consists of Section 4 which presents the resulting LINDDUN threat model for this application case.

¹ Kurtoglu2025.

² The content presented in this report mainly corresponds to Section 7.2.2, and 7.3, in conjunction with Appendices A and B of the master's thesis.

Part I

Case description

2 *Scope and inputs*

Unlike traditional payment environments, festival payment systems operate in temporary, high-volume settings, where payment infrastructure, data handling practices and security measures can differ significantly. To gain a deeper understanding of these systems, this section analyzes various festivals and their respective payment technologies, compiling key details into a structured dataset. Section 6.1 outlines the selection process of the festivals examined. Section 6.2 provides an overview of the festivals analyzed and their payment technologies, as well as the cashless payment providers analyzed and their privacy & data practices.

2.1 *Selection of Festivals*

Cashless payment systems at festivals vary widely, with different events adopting distinct technologies based on infrastructure, security requirements and user convenience. To analyze these systems, a dataset of various festivals is compiled.

In selecting festivals for this study, a structured approach is followed to ensure a diverse and representative dataset. The selection criteria were based on four key considerations:

- **Availability of Data:** One of the key factors in selecting festivals was the availability of publicly accessible information regarding their payment systems. Data was gathered from official festival websites and payment provider documentation to ensure the accuracy of this analysis. This ensures that the findings are based on verifiable data.
- **Diversity in Festival Genre and Size:** The selected festivals represent a broad range of genres (electronic, rock, metal, pop, hip-hop) and sizes (from small 12,000-attendee festivals to large-scale events like Glastonbury and Coachella). This diversity ensures that this study captures a variety of festival payment use cases.
- **Belgium as a Festival-Dominant Country:** Belgium has a rich festival culture and hosts some of the most well-known music events in Europe, such as Tomorrowland, Rock Werchter and Pukkelpop. The country has a high adoption rate of cashless payment systems at festivals, making it an ideal ecosystem to study the different payment technologies in use. Additionally, Belgium's festival industry

operates under structured regulations, providing insights into how cashless payment systems function in well-regulated environments (e.g., the GDPR) or the use of proprietary payment systems, issued by the FOD Economie [3, 1, 2].

- **Inclusion of International Festivals for Comparison:** While Belgium serves as the focal point of scoping for this case study, festivals from other countries (USA, UK, Germany, Spain, Japan, Hungary and France) are also included in support of a more complete comparative analysis.

2.2 Overview of Festivals and Payment Providers

Table 3 (in Appendix) provides an overview of the selected Belgian and international festivals, their location, size, payment technology and external payment provider. To enhance clarity, selected festivals are categorized. Examining the festival dataset reveals the following insights regarding payment system usage:

Technology Categories of Investigated Festivals	Percentage (%)
NFC	69.6%
Mobile Payment	21.7%
Physical Systems (Coins, Vouchers, Tokens)	17.4%
Regular Cards	17.4%

Table 1: Analysis of Cashless Payment Systems Used by Investigated Festivals

- A total of 23 festivals were analyzed, with 60.9% of them taking place in Belgium. As highlighted in Table 1, the most widely used payment technology is based on NFC. This observed trend aligns with the initial justification for focusing on Belgium, given its high adoption rate of cashless technologies at festivals.
- Physical payment systems such as vouchers were found in 17.4% of festivals. While these traditional methods are still in use, they are gradually being replaced by more modern technologies. Events like Pukkelpop (Belgium) and Alcatraz Festival (Belgium) still use drink or food vouchers, which minimize digital security risks but introduce issues such as loss, counterfeiting and inefficiencies in tracking transactions [4]. Notably, some festivals offer multiple payment options, which were counted in all relevant categories.

To better understand how festival payment systems operate, a selection of payment providers is analyzed, offering cashless payment solutions relevant to the European festival landscape. Table 3 (in

Appendix A.2) presents an overview of their cashless payment technology offerings and stated privacy/data practices, based on publicly available information.

An analysis of these providers reveals variations in their stated practices. While some explicitly claim GDPR compliance (e.g., NFC-tron, Playpass/Weezevent) and offer user control features (e.g., apps for balance checking or refund requests), others emphasize organizer-focused data analytics and insights derived from tracking attendee transactions and behavior (e.g., Tappit and Oveit). Several providers did not explicitly mention GDPR compliance in the reviewed materials. Furthermore, differences in implementation, such as wristbands vs mobile-based payments or registered vs unregistered usage, impact the level of security and data exposure. Understanding these providers' approaches helps assess the risks and benefits of various festival payment systems, although actual compliance and internal data handling practices require deeper investigation beyond publicly available statements.

3 *Modeling of Data Flow Diagrams*

We provide an abstraction of the information systems used in the context of a cashless NFC-based payment system. Some assumptions and scoping decisions:

1. The payment service is operated by a third-party technology and service provider (the 'Cashless Payment Provider'). This is an organization that provides the hardware (NFC wristbands and NFC terminals) and implements the functionality for topping up and payment in the in-festival context.
2. Realistically (e.g., in a transition phase), and depending on the context, there may or may not alternative payment means available (e.g., cash, bank-led payment). In this case study, the cashless, NFC-based payment is the only option offered to a festival attendee.
3. Festival attendees have to top-up their account balance, which is a payment transaction. This can be done during the festival, or beforehand.
4. As payment transactions occur in high frequency and volume in a festival, a system of *vendor payment settlement* is implemented at lower frequency: during the festival, all payments are recorded by the system, but they are settled in large volume or in bulk, i.e. the actual payments to the vendors occur at fixed intervals (e.g. end

of day/festival). This process is also called 'deferred net settlement' (DNS).

3.1 Data Flow Diagrams

Rather than focusing on the specific communication technology used and the specifics of the communication protocols, the DFD models focus on the broader information system, involving the steps to (i) register attendees at the basis of their festival ticket, (ii) linking a payment wristband to such attendee, (iii) the procedure to top up the festival account balance via a third-party payment providers, and (iv) and performing purchases and in-festival transactions.

Figure 1 details the overall process of Vendor registration. Figure 2 then presents the first DFD that depicts the flows related to registration and activation of the Festival attendee into the relevant systems, which is highly analogous.

Figure 1: DFD of the contactless Festival Payment system: Vendor registration and Vendor payment terminal activation.

Figure 3 then presents the DFD of the festival payment system that illustrates the flows related to topping up the account balancing and performing contactless payments at the festival.

Finally, Figure 4 presents the process of payment settlement to the Vendors.

Figure 2: DFD of the contactless Festival Payment system: registration and activation.

Figure 3: DFD of the contactless Festival Payment system: transactions (top-up and payment).

Figure 4: DFD of the contactless Festival Payment system: settlement of Vendor payments.

3.2 Data Flows: Step by step

Vendor registration and activation. The following data flows are used to register vendors in the system. These steps may occur in preparation of the festival, and may only be executed for legitimate vendors and within the boundaries of a legal contract with the festival organizer.

- V1. The Vendor registers their name, contact details and bank account information
 - V1.1. This information is stored in the Vendor Registration DB operated by the Festival Organizer.
 - V1.2. The Festival Organizer automatically registers the Vendor with the Cashless Payment Provider.
 - V1.2.1. The Vendor information is recorded in the Cashless Account DB.
- V2. The Vendor associates their NFC-capable payment terminal to their account³.
 - V2.1. The NFC payment terminal information is recorded in the Cashless Account DB and linked to the vendor (VendorID).

³ We do not model any form of authentication or authorization of the Vendor in these systems, as these concerns are considered out of scope of this privacy threat model.

Festival attendee registration and activation. The following data flows are used in the process of registering at the festival and activating the cashless payment modalities, as depicted above in Figure 2. These steps may occur in preparation of the festival, e.g. at home, via a website, or upon gaining entrance at the festival.

A1. The Festival attendee registers or checks in at the festival (e.g., ticket verification or registration booth) by presenting a valid ticket (TicketNb) and means of identification (here the Name, and Email⁴).

⁴ This may be extended or broadened to other identifiers, e.g. the social security number (SSID).

A1.1. This leads to the write attendee record data flow, which leads to persisting or updating the record and activation of the ticket in the Festival Registration DB

A1.2. Then, as part of the registration process, the festival system redirects to the system of the Cashless Payment Providers, more specifically to activate the cashless account (activate cashless account data flow to the Create Cashless Account process).

A1.2.1. This leads to the initial registration of the Festival attendee in the Cashless Account DB database of the Cashless Payment Provider, with Name, Email and AttendeeID.

A2. After handing a physical NFC bracelet to the Festival attendee, the registration of that bracelet (and association to the Festival attendee) happens via the link bracelet data flow to the Link NFC Bracelet process.

A2.1. The NFC payment bracelet information is recorded in the Cashless Account DB and linked to the festival attendee (AttendeeID).

Top-up transactions. The following data flows are used in the process of topping up the account balance as depicted in the top half of Figure 3.

TU1. The Festival attendee requests a top-up (request top-up data flow).

TU1.1. The Top-up Service process fetches the relevant information (Name,Email) in the Cashless Account DB, based on the provided AttendeeId.

TU1.2. The Top-up Service process then sends a payment request to the External Payment provider, by requesting a payment transaction (request payment transaction which returns a TransactionID) and requests a financial transaction (request payment transaction data flow) of the given Amount from the Festival attendee to the Destination account of the Cashless Payment Provider.

TU1.3. The Payment Processor issues a callback via payment authorization with the same TransactionID indicating success of the request financial transaction.

TU1.4. The Top-up Service process issues a increase balance for AttendeeID with the exact Amount paid to the Update Cashless Balance process.

B1. The Update Cashless Balance process updates the balance for the festival attendee with AttendeeID in the Cashless Account DB, through the update balance data flow.

B2. The transaction is logged in the Transaction Log data store through the log transaction data flow.] item[]

Festival payments. In-festival payments happen as follows through the following data flows depicted in the bottom half of Figure 3.

P1. The Vendor initiates the transaction by entering RefId and Amount

P2. The Festival attendee confirms the payment, by tapping the wristband to the payment terminal.

P3. The account balance is updated accordingly; the account balance is reduced with the paid amount:

B1. The Update Cashless Balance process updates the balance (negatively) for the festival attendee with AttendeeID in the Cashless Account DB, through the update balance data flow.

B1.b The same data flow Update Cashless Balance is used to positively update the balance of the Vendor's account in the Cashless Account DB.

B2. The transactions are logged in the Transaction Log data store through the log transaction data flow.

Vendor payment settlement. Finally, the flows depicted in Figure 4 implement the following logic:

VS1. At a predefined time slot (e.g., end of day), the Settlement Service initiates the process. For each Vendor (VendorID), a list of open (unpaid) transactions is fetched, with per transaction the RefId and Amount and the vendor details (Name, Email, BankAccount).

VS2. The Settlement Service process then sends a payment request to the External Payment provider, by requesting a payment transaction (request payment transaction which returns a TransactionID) and requests a financial transaction (request payment transaction data flow) of the given Amount to the Vendor's BankAccount.

VS3. The Payment Processor issues a callback via payment authorization with the same TransactionID indicating success of the request financial transaction.

VS4. The Settlement Service marks the transactions (RefIDs) as paid and closed, and attaches the corresponding TransactionID to the database records.

3.3 DFD Glossary

This glossary provides a standalone explanation of the different architectural elements of the contactless festival payment system (external entities, processes and data stores).

External entities.

Festival attendee. The customer of the festival is an entity of the payment system which represents the end-user that will use the cashless payment system.

Vendor. The Vendor is an abstraction of the diverse payment beneficiaries that can use the system in the festival context (e.g., food and drinks shops, etc).

Payment Processor. The payment processor represents a traditional, third-party bank-led payment system (e.g., credit or debit-card based) that authorizes and performs the monetary transactions, and submits confirmation callback when upon transaction completion.

Processes.

Attendee Registration. The Festival attendee needs to register either physically, or via the app or website of the festival, by entering their personal information.

Create Cashless Account. The Festival attendee activates a cashless account, which is stored in the Cashless Account DB.

Link NFC Bracelet. The NFC bracelet is linked to the Festival attendee, e.g., by scanning the bracelet's QR code on the bracelet or presenting it to a registration terminal.

Top-up Service. This process regulates the logic that allows the Festival attendee to top-up (increase) their account balance.

NFC Payment. This process implements the transaction logic of an in-festival payment and orchestrates the execution of a payment transaction between Festival attendee and Vendor.

Update Cashless Balance. By topping-up or NFC payment, the balance of the account is updated in the Cashless Account DB. Each transaction is also logged in the Transaction Log DB.

Settlement Service. This process implements the vendor settlement logic. It is automatically invoked at regular time intervals, initiates payment transactions to each vendor using the Payment Processor and implements the corresponding bookkeeping logic.

Data stores.

Festival Registration DB. The festival organizer owns and operates this database, which includes the personal information of registered Festival attendees, and maintains the link to sold festival tickets. It also stored information related to the registered Vendors at the festival.

Cashless Account DB. NFC accounts, updated balance fields and cashless account information are all deposited in the cashless account database. The database operates within the trust boundary of the cashless payment provider.

Transaction Log. All records regarding payment transactions are stored in this transaction log. This includes information regarding the amount and Festival attendee that have topped up their account balance.

Part II

Privacy threat models

4 Privacy Threats

The table below lists the privacy threats that were established on basis of multi-rater consensus (consensus level shown in final column). The specific LINDDUN threat characteristics used are shown in the penultimate column.

Threat location	Embraced threat description	Characteristics	Consensus
LINKING			
A1. register (Name, Email, TicketNb): AttendeeID	All attendee interactions are linked through the unique system-generated identifier (attendeeID).	L.1.1	3
A1.2. activate cashless account (Name, Email, AttendeeID)	The cashless account creation is linked through the unique system generated identifier (attendeeID). This may allow inference that a certain person is a user of cashless system, learning properties such as tech-savviness.	L.1.1; L.2.2.1	4
A2. link bracelet (AttendeeID, NFC_ID)	Both the attendeeID and the NFC_ID are unique identifiers, these are furthermore linked together by the application. Any subsequent use of the NFC_ID in payment transactions can then be directly linked to the attendee as well.	L.1.1	3
P1. Initiate NFC Payment Transaction (VendorID, RefID, Amount)	This (Unique Identifier) may be used to infer vendor stall popularity; sales and purchase information may be subject to profiling, clustering, learning trends or specifics about an individual.	L.2.1.2; L.2.2.1; L.2.2.3; L.1.1	3
P2. Payment confirmation (NFC_ID, Amount): boolean (crossing boundary)	The attendee-specific unique NFC_IDs in payment request make it trivial to link all payment confirmations to the same individual. Frequency of these messages may allow inferring consumer profile/habits.	L.2.2.1; L.1.1	4
TU1. Request top-up (AttendeeID, Amount)	The top-up has a unique attendee identifiers that makes it trivial to link top-up requests to the same user. Frequency of these messages may allow inferring consumer profile/habits.	L.2.2.1; L.1.1	4
IDENTIFYING			

A1. register (Name, Email, TicketNb) : AttendeeID	The attendee registration contains identified information (Full name and Email Adress, Unique Identifier). These data are not necessary for the service.	I.1.1; I.2.1.1	3
A1.2. activate cashless account (Name, Email, AttendeeID)	The cashless account activation contains identified data (Full name and Email Address, Unique Identifier).	I.1.1; I.2.1.1	3
A2. link bracelet (AttendeeID, NFC_ID)	The NFC_ID serves as an identifier (Unique Identifier) for the users, as it uniquely refers to the specific individual with the cashless account.	I.2.1.1	3
P2. Payment confirmation (NFC_ID, Amount): boolean (crossing boundary)	The payment confirmation transaction has a unique identifier linked to the data subject (NFC_ID can be used to identify the holder), which allows the system to determine the identity of the payer.	I.2.1.1	3
TU1. Request top-up (AttendeeID, Amount)	The top-up request contains an attendeeID that is linked to the identity of the data subject (Unique Identifier).	I.2.1.1	3
TU1.2. request payment transaction (Name, Email, Amount, Destination) : TransactionID	The payment request contains identified data that is sent to the third party (Full name and Email Adress). It may be sufficient to request payment transaction at the basis of pseudonym (e.g bank account, authorization happens out of scope anyway).	I.1.1	4

NON-REPUDIATION

A1. register (Name, Email, TicketNb) : AttendeeID	Registration of the attendee keeps a record of the individual attending the festival and impacts their plausible deniability.	Nr.1.1	3
A1.2. activate cashless account (Name, Email, AttendeeID)	The activation of the cashless account, together with the attendeeID, links all their spending to their attendences of a specific festival; impacting their plausible deniability about attending and spending there.	Nr.1.1	3
P2. Payment confirmation (NFC_ID, Amount): boolean (crossing boundary)	All transactions are logged and linked to the individual user. This impacts the individuals denability claims on their participation in the festival and the types and amounts of purchases they made. Payment confirmation is an action with attributable side-effects, in some rare cases there may be a desire to have plausible deniability (e.g. minor person buying anticonception at festival with a desire to hide it from others/parents).	Nr.2; Nr.1.1	3
V1. register (Name, Email, BankAccount): VendorID	The presence of a small set of vendors may impact an individual's plausible deniability claims on purchasing goods from a certain company. Vendor can not deny his attendance at the festival.	Nr.1.1; Nr.2	3

DETECTING

TU1.3. payment authorization (TransactionID)	The response (perhaps declined) may allow the Cashless Payment Provider learn something about the financial situation of the attendee. The poayment authorization or lack thereof may provide additional information (e.g., insufficient balance) that allows the cashelss payment provider to learn more information about the attendee.	D.3	4
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UNAWARENESS

A1. register (Name, Email, TicketNb): AttendeeID	The festival attendee may be given insufficient controls about how their payment data is processed, stored, used. Data Subject has no way of setting preferences, getting access to their data or correcting/deleting it.	U.2.1; U.2.2; U.2.3	3
A1.2. activate cashless account (Name, Email, AttendeeID)	The attendee may not be aware that their cashless account creation is linked to their full identity details, hence all transactions on their cashless account are linked to their identity. Furthermore, they may not have access to their cashless account's transaction history. The festival attendee may be unaware that their payment data is shared to third parties other than the festival organizer: the Cashless payment provider, the vendor and the third-party payment processor.	U.1.1; U.2.1; U.2.2; U.2.3	4
TU1.2. request payment transaction (Name, Email, Amount, Destination): TransactionID	The user does not a have to configure or control how and how much of their data is shared with the third party payment provider. Data Subject has no way of setting preferences, getting access to their data or correcting/deleting it.	U.2.1; U.2.2; U.2.3	3

NON-COMPLIANCE

A1. register (Name, Email, TicketNb): AttendeeID	No method for withdrawing consent, If not deleted immediately after the festival personal information might be stored unnecessarily long. Attendee may not be given proper controls to unsubscribe, etc; data may be kept forever or too long. The registration collects and processes more data than necessary for providing a cashless account.	Nc.1.1.1; Nc.1.1.4; Nc.1.1.2; Nc.1.1.3.1	3
TU1.2. request payment transaction (Name, Email, Amount, Destination): TransactionID	No method for withdrawing consent, If not deleted immediately after the festival personal information might be stored unnecessarily long. Attendee may not be given proper controls to unsubscribe, etc; data may be kept forever or too long. The registration collects and processes more data than necessary for providing a cashless account.	Nc.1.1.3.1; Nc.1.1.4; Nc.1.1.2	3

V1. register(Name, Email, BankAccount): VendorID	Vendor may not be aware of involvement of third parties; Vendor's data may be kept forever. Withdrawing content impossible.	Nc.1.1; Nc.1.1.4; Nc.1.1.3.1	3
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References

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- [2] Maïthé Chini. *Cashless wristbands? Belgian festivals not allowed to make profit from own payment systems*. <https://www.brusselstimes.com/1079010/cashless-wristbands-belgian-festivals-not-allowed-to-make-profit-from-own-payment-systems>. Accessed: 25 April 2025. 2024.
- [3] FOD Economie. *Het gebruik van eigen betaalmiddelen op evenementen: guidelines voor organisatoren*. <https://economie.fgov.be/nl/themas/ondernemingen/guidance/andere-sectoren/het-gebruik-van-eigen>. Accessed: 2025-04-25. 2024.
- [4] Yong Wang, Christen Hahn, and Kruttika Sutrave. "Mobile payment security, threats, and challenges". In: *2016 Second International Conference on Mobile and Secure Services (MobiSecServ)*. 2016, pp. 1–5. DOI: 10.1109/MOBISECSERV.2016.7440226.

A List of festivals

A.1 Belgian Festivals

Alcatraz Festival

Size Info: <https://www.vrt.be/vrtnws/nl/2024/08/09/metalfestival-alcatraz-in-kortrijk-verwacht-recordopkomst-van-55/>

Accessed: 2025-03-27

Technology Used: <https://www.grimmgent.com/festival-guides/#food-drinks>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Couleur Café

Size Info: <https://www.bruzz.be/ice/ice/couleur-cafe-2024-zo-waardevol-als-divers-festival-met-ruimte-voor-onbewaakte-momenten-2024>

Accessed: 2025-03-27

Technology Used: <https://www.couleurcafe.be/nl/praktisch/faq>

Accessed: 2025-03-27

Dour Festival

Size Info: <https://www.brusselstimes.com/1151094/the-34th-dour-festival-ends-on-a-high-note-averaging-over-44000-visitors-per-day>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.dourfestival.eu/en/faq/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://www.dourfestival.eu/en/terms-and-conditions/>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Graspop Metal Meeting

Size Info: <https://festileaks.com/festival/graspop/2024/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.graspop.be/en/info/cashless>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://www.graspop.be/en/info/terms-and-conditions>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Les Ardentes

Size Info: <https://www.belganewsagency.eu/festival-les-ardentes-in-liege-expects-to-welcome-around-220000-people>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://lesardentes.be/info/cashless>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://lesardentes.be/terms-and-conditions?lng=en>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Lokerse Feesten

Size Info: <https://festileaks.com/festival/lokerse-feesten/2024/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.lokersefeesten.be/nl/praktisch/eten-drinken>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://weezevent.com/en-gb/story/lokerse-feesten/>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Pukkelpop

Size Info: <https://www.pukkelpop.be/en/about-pukkelpop>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.pukkelpop.be/nl/info/veelgestelde-vragen>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Rampage Open Air

Size Info: <https://www.vrt.be/vrtnws/nl/2024/07/05/dit-wordt-rampage-open-air/>

Accessed: 2025-03-27

Technology Used: <https://www.rampageopenair.eu/faq>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://www.rampageopenair.eu/internal-regulations>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Rock Herk

Size Info: https://dumpmagazine.be/ShowNews/Festival_report__Rock_Herk_2024

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://rockherk.be/nl/praktisch>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Rock Werchter

Size Info: <https://www.brusselstimes.com/584386/rock-werchter-90000-daily-visitors-and-100-artists-over-four-days>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.rockwerchter.be/nl/cashless>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://www.rockwerchter.be/nl/cashless>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Suikerrock

Size Info: <https://www.demorgen.be/nieuws/suikerrock-krijgt-meer-dan-100-000-bezoekers-over-de-vloer-b639776c/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.suikerrock.be/praktisch/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://www.suikerrock.be/algemene-voorwaarden/>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Tomorrowland

Size Info: <https://www.tomorrowland.com/home/article/tomorrowland-belgium-2023-aftermovie/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://faq.tomorrowland.com/hc/en-us/sections/360007281732-Cashless>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://belgium.tomorrowland.com/en/sales-info/your-privacy/privacy-policy/>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

TW Classic

Size Info: <https://festileaks.com/festival/tw-classic/2024/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.twclassic.be/nl/cashless>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: https://www.twclassic.be/en/conditions-of-sale?_gl=1*cg2fx0*_up*MQ..*_ga*MjkwNjQ3NDMzLjE3NDc2Njc2MDA.*_ga_HBZ7RJPkZ3*cze3NDc2Njc10TkkbzEkZzAkdDE3NDc2Njc10TkkajAkbDAkaDA

Accessed: 2025-05-19

wecandance

Size Info: https://www.nieuwsblad.be/cnt/dmf20240812_94070182

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://wecandance.be/info-faq/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://wecandance.be/terms-conditions/>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

A.2 *International Festivals*

Balaton Sound (Hungary)

Size Info: <https://www.maximaltrips.com/blog/balaton-sound/why-balaton-sound>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://balatonsound.com/en/festival-info#!8979/how-to-top-up-a-wristband>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://festipay.com/author/marci/#:~:text=Ingenico%20Group%2C%20the%20global%20leader,Sound%20Festival%20and%20VOLT%20Festival.>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Coachella (USA)

Size Info: <https://english.elpais.com/culture/2024-04-12/coachella-2024-will-be-one-of-the-most-latino-editions-in-history-schedules-performances-and-where-to-watch-it.html>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.coachella.com/faq>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

FIB Bencássim (Spain)

Size Info: <https://festileaks.com/festival/fib-benicassim/2024/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://weezevent.com/en-gb/weezpay/cashless/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://weezevent.com/en-gb/weezpay/cashless/>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Glastonbury (UK)

Size Info: <https://festileaks.com/festival/glastonbury-festival/2024/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.glastonburyfestivals.co.uk/info/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Fuji Rock Festival (Japan)

Size Info: <https://en.fujirockfestival.com/2024/0730a/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://en.fujirockfestival.com/2024/guide>

/faq/

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Lollapalooza (Germany)

Size Info: <https://www.fox32chicago.com/news/lollapalooza-2024-kicks-off-grant-park-drawing-huge-crowds-top-artists>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://www.lollapaloozade.com/en/cashless-agbs>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://www.lollapaloozade.com/en/cashlessagbs>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Rolling Loud (Global)

Technology Used: <https://europe.rollingloud.com/cashless-en/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: https://portugal.rollingloud.com/terms/payment_plan_terms

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Sziget (Hungary)

Size Info: <https://www.ticketfairy.com/word/2024/12/24/biggest-music-festivals-of-2024-in-the-world/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://szigetfestival.com/en/festival-info>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

External Payment Provider: <https://szigetfestival.com/en/festival-info#!/2380/paying-at-the-festival>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Tomorrowland Winter (France)

Size Info: <https://winter.tomorrowland.com/en/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://winter.tomorrowland.com/en/my-bracelet/cashless-information/>

Accessed: 2025-02-15

Technology Used: <https://winter.tomorrowland.com/en/practical/general-terms-and-conditions/>

Accessed: 2025-05-19

Festival Name	Country	Size (/ day)	Technology Used	External Payment Provider
Alcatraz Festival	Belgium	18,000	Physical Vouchers	-
Couleur Café	Belgium	24,000	Physical Vouchers / Payconiq	-
Dour Festival	Belgium	44,000	NFC with QR	Weezevent
Graspop Metal Meeting	Belgium	55,000	NFC with QR	Undisclosed
Les Ardentes	Belgium	55,000	NFC with QR	Weezevent
Lokerse Feesten	Belgium	15,000	NFC with QR	Weezevent
Pukkelpop	Belgium	66,000	Physical Vouchers	-
Rampage Open Air	Belgium	18,000	NFC with QR	Undisclosed
Rock Herk	Belgium	12,500	Physical Vouchers	-
Rock Werchter	Belgium	90,000	NFC with QR	Weezevent
Suikerrock	Belgium	25,000	NFC	Undisclosed
Tomorrowland	Belgium	67,000	NFC	Undisclosed
TW Classic	Belgium	60,000	NFC with QR	Undisclosed
WECANDANCE	Belgium	13,500	NFC with QR	Weezevent
Balaton Sound	Hungary	50,000	NFC / Regular Card / Mobile Payment	Festipay
Coachella	USA	125,000	Regular Card / Mobile Payment	-
FIB Bencássim	Spain	53,000	NFC with QR	Weezevent
Glastonbury	UK	150,000	Regular Card / Mobile Payment	-
Fuji Rock Festival	Japan	24,000	Regular Card / Mobile Payment	-
Lollapalooza	Germany	100,000	NFC	Weezevent
Rolling Loud	Varies	-	NFC with QR	Weezevent
Sziget	Hungary	70,000	NFC with QR	Festipay
Tomorrowland Winter	France	4,000	NFC	Undisclosed

Table 3: Overview of Payment Systems at Selected Belgian and International Festivals. Sources for festival size and technology used can be found in Appendix A.1 and Appendix A.2.